

Work Safety Protection for Labors: Obstacle of Implementation in Province of East Kalimantan (Case study on PT. Elkaka and PT. Wemiin)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 25, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: January 22, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Implementation, Obstacle, Labor, Occupational Health and Safety</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4457851</p>	<p><i>Purpose: Describing labor obstacle in the implementation of work safety protection on PT. Elkaka and PT. Wemiin. Methodology: This research uses qualitative research by looking for natural information from a case (Patton, 2002), subsequent research produces descriptive data (Taylor, Bogdan & DeVault, 2016). The informants in this research are general manager, health safety and environmental manager, human resource development manager and two supporting labors. Findings: Obstacles found will affect the program to implement occupational safety and health policies and the work environment. These constraints are labor behavior, company support policies and the availability of company facilities. Significant: Labors on PT. Elkaka and PT. Wein currently doesn't know more about the regulations regarding a safe work environment.</i></p>

Introduction

Hazardous work is usually found in the industrial sectors of agriculture, construction, forestry, fisheries and mining (International Labor Organization). Every year for all industrial sectors work accidents still occur. In Indonesia in all industrial sectors, from 2014 to 2017 work accidents increased (BPJS Employment).

The mineral and coal mining sector is a high-risk industry category or commonly referred to as the extractive industry (EITI Indonesia 2016). Based on data from work accidents in the mineral and coal sector in East Kalimantan Province, there are still mineral and coal sector companies that have not yet implemented company policies.

Work safety protection policies in the long-term are important in reducing the level of life force and are able to protect the success of economic growth that has been achieved (Kim, Lee and Reynolds, 2012). Occupational accident is a situation that is clearly undesirable and often unexpected at first, it can cause losses both time, property and casualties that occur in an industrial work process (Tarwaka, 2014). The high number of work accidents is caused by several factors, they are high workload, large work capacity, and uncontrolled work environment (Barlasa & Izcip, 2018).

In the context of mineral and coal companies, the researcher uses the theory of value-based aspects of equality, equity (Gilbert and Terrell, 1993) and based criteria which has efficiency, effectiveness. Furthermore Janson (1998) says that the factor that influence the implementation of the policy one of them is the human resource factor.

Furthermore, Obstacle to work safety protection policies and development of labor protection policies regarding obstacles to work safety protection policies are applied to the mineral and coal sector industries. So there is still room for study on obstacles to work safety protection in the mineral and coal industry sector in East Kalimantan Province.

Literature Review

Labor protection is a government control mechanism so that good and tight labor protection will reduce the work termination (Nasr HB, 2015). Furthermore, Soepomo, 2003 states that labor protection is a guarantee that must be obtained by the labor from the employer, so that their safety and welfare during work can be protected. For this reason, Soepomo, 2003 divides labor protection into three types of protection, namely economic protection, social protection and work safety protection. Besides getting a wage or salary, labor is also provided with benefits which is determined by the employer or the company where they work. These benefits include transportation benefits, family benefits and holiday benefits (Widowati, 2010).

Labor protection is a type of social protection that intends to protect or take care of the labor from workplace incidents or conditions that are harmful to health and decency in the case that the labor do their work

(Mokodompis, 2016). Furthermore, Mokodompis 2016 states that the protection of work safety has specific rules which regulates work safety, that is, every labor has the right to get protection in doing work for the welfare of life and to increase production, and the safety of every labor who is in the workplace needs to be guaranteed as well. Tawiah KA 2016 says that labor is not only committed to the organization, but labor expects to think first about the needs of occupational safety and health by institutionalizing good and healthy policies. Moreover, Silvestre 2008 states that the labor compensation system can contribute to reduce workplace accidents, where labor compensation is designed and implemented as an economic incentive for employers to invest in safety and cooperation between employers and labors through so-called safety first.

Occupational safety and health at work need innovation so as to bring sustainable development through healthy people, safe workplaces, reducing accident costs, controlled environments, managed work accidents and increase safety knowledge in the workplace (Jilcha, Kitaw. 2016). To realize all about safety in work, the leader is a role model that must be exemplary, work ethic, responsibility, integrity, transparent, consistent, motivated and open space for discussion and effective communication to create a zero accident. The implementation of safety in working in every industry is very dependent on the commitment of the top management in developing safety culture in their respective organizations (Astuti, 2010). Furthermore, what is said by Usep, Anggraini & Made, 2016 that the safety leadership model with participating and delegating styles can create a climate of safety and behavior towards labor safety procedure.

Haslinda, 2016 states that with effective accident management, it is hoped that accidents can be reduced and knowledge also awareness about occupational safety and health can be improved. So that, safety training, company policy and communication in the context of effective accident management. For that, Barlasa B, Izcib FB. 2018 says that the risk of work accidents is significantly related to individual factors and workplace.

Friedrich, 1963 says that policy as an action that leads to the goals proposed by a person, group or government in a particular environment in connection with certain obstacles while looking for opportunities to achieve goals or realize the desired goals. Furthermore the outline of social policy is manifested in three categories namely legislation, government regulations, regional regulations, social service programs, and taxation systems (Midgley, 2000). Midgley further assumes that based on this category, it can be stated that every legislation, law or local regulation concerning social issues and life is a form of social policy. For this reason, Zastrow, 2010 says that social welfare is to meet the social, economic, health and recreational needs of every individual in the society. Social welfare seeks to improve social functioning at all ages, both belonging to the poor and the rich.

Furthermore, said by Blackmore and Griggs (2007) who define that the goal of social policy is an effort to improve social welfare and meet individual needs such as, education, health, housing, and social security. Meeting individual needs and increasing social welfare show that the value of social justice is very thick in social policy. Opinion expressed by Jamrozik 2001 about the definition of social policy is a mechanism to allocate resources available to the society so that they can achieve certain outcome goals in accordance with the dominant value of the society and the goals and objectives of the policy that has been determined.

Another opinion regarding social policy by Chambers & Wedel (2005: 57-59) about the value critical appraisal. There are three types of social policy assessments: the first is the type that uses social problem analysis as a reference. This type emphasizes that the completion of the assessment of social policies and programs can have an impact on social problems. Second, the type that uses the traditional value perspective such as equality value, equity value, adequacy value. And third, the type that use certain policy elements.

Furthermore, Gilbert and Terrell (1993: 55-58) states that social policy can be done with a choice of values and criteria. These aspects of choice include determining the beneficiaries (bases allocation), choice in determining the programs offered (social provision), choice in determining the delivery strategy of the program (delivery system), and choice in determining funding (finance). The four value-based aspects include: (a) aspects of equality value, namely equalizing the distribution of resources and opportunities for labor in obtaining protection guarantees, (b) aspects of equity value, namely understanding of the fair treatment of labor protection rights; (c) aspects of adequacy value, namely satisfaction in providing services that are physically and spiritually appropriate without regard to whether the allocation of benefits is equal or different to labor, and the implementation of a criteria-based policies include; (a) efficiency, namely the protection policy chosen based on the most cost-effective consideration, (b) the aspect of effectiveness, namely the choice of alternative protection programs that provide the best benefits for labor, (c) the cost-effective aspect of the choice of programs based on an analysis of the cost and effectiveness of the policy programs, and; (d) the cost-benefit aspect that is measuring the benefits received by labor compared to the costs incurred (Chambers & Wedel, 2005).

Labor safety policies in the context of social policy responsibilities for larger companies must have positive work attitudes, especially organizational commitment. For this reason, companies must establish labor safety policies that include training. This policy must aim to create a positive safety climate and risk prevention culture by emphasizing management's commitment to labor safety protection. The policy is an important part of the company's internal responsibilities, namely a positive impact on safety performance and avoiding accidents

with high costs, enhancement of the work attitude and enhancement of the work motivation and safety commitments (Hadjimanolis, Barusta. 2013).

This research uses qualitative research by finding naturalistic information from certain cases (Patton, 2002). Furthermore, this research produces descriptive data. Moreover, the researcher uses case studies as research approach because the researcher wants to understand social phenomena on a small scale in a natural situation (Bloor and Wood, 2006). For this reason, the researcher investigates carefully the activities, processes, or groups of individuals (Creswell, 2009). The informant is someone who knows and understands the type of information (Given, 2008: 430). The informants in this research are the general manager, health safety, environmental manager, human resource development manager and two labor.

Methodology

Pada penelitian ini menggunakan pendekatan kualitatif dengan cara mencari informasi secara naturalistik dari kasus tertentu (Patton, 2002). Selanjutnya penelitian ini menghasilkan data yang deskriptif. Lebih lanjut peneliti menggunakan studi kasus sebagai pendekatan penelitian karena peneliti hendak memahami fenomena sosial dalam skala kecil suatu keadaan alamiah (Bloor dan Wood, 2006). Untuk itu peneliti menyelidiki secara cermat aktivitas, proses, atau sekelompok individu (Creswell, 2009). Informan yaitu seseorang mengetahui dan memahami jenis informasi (Given, 2008:430). Adapun informan pada penelitian ini yaitu *general manager, health safety and environmental manager, human resource development manager* dan 2 orang Pekerja.

Analysis and Discussion

Implementation of policies on health and occupational health and work environment on PT. Elkaka and PT. Wemiin conducted by labor can be seen from the obstacles in implementing the policies felt by the company. As for labor knowledge and in implementing occupational safety and health policies and the work environment, it can also be found that there are obstacles of the implementation of occupational safety, health policies and the work environment felt by PT. Elkaka and PT. Wemiin, when implementing the occupational safety and health policy.

From the practice finding, it can be known that there are obstacles to the implementation of policies felt by the company when implementing occupational safety and health policies and the work environment. These obstacles include labor behavior, company support policies and the availability of company facilities. These three things are known by the company to affect alternative choices in implementing the policy. Alternative choices taken by companies in the bases allocation category are beneficiaries for all workforce (universal), alternative choices in social provision are what will be accepted by those who meet the criteria and qualify (eligible), alternative choices in the delivery system must be invited to cooperate in the context of service delivery (free-standing), as well as an alternative choice in finance is how to determine budgeting in the company.

It can be explained that the behavior of company labors who tend not to pay attention to regulations and do not care about the conditions of the work environment affect the company's alternatives in the category of bases allocation (recipient of the program) and social provision (determining the program). The company considers that the recipients of the programs and services are the entire workforce of the company. It shows that the labor force does not currently know more about regulations regarding a safe work environment. These conditions are the cause of the emergence of work safety protection problems in companies. With the existence of the occupational safety and health policy and work environment policies, it is expected that the problems of occupational safety protection and environmental protection caused by structuring the work environment are less safe and will be resulted. In addition, the implementation of the policy will also encourage relevant departments in the company to be more concerned with the conditions of the company's work environment. These obstacles regarding labor behavior are felt by labors as obstacles in implementing policies. So, the company also prefers to design concrete programs and services that are directly related to the problems that exist in the company, such as work safety protection programs that are expected to be able to result the problems of workplace workplace accidents in the company.

Likewise with obstacles regarding the implementation of the policy itself, it is known by the company as incomplete and still needs to be evaluated. This condition also affects the programs and services designed by the relevant departments. Where, the relevant departments prioritize programs and services that are concrete or involved by the company. The company knows that the implementation of occupational safety and health policies and the work environment still requires many improvements. However, improving the implementation of the policy can only be done after the policy is implemented. The company understands that the implementation of the policy will be less than optimal, because improvements or improvements to the policy have not been made.

The availability of supporting facilities affects companies choosing to involve relevant departments and companies as a source of budgeting and plan for the delivery of the program strategy. Knowledge of the availability of supporting facilities felt by the company will be able to hamper the implementation of occupational safety and health policies and work environment. In fact, programs and services designed by related departments such as the occupational, health, safety and environmental (OHSE) department, human resources (HR) department, operational department and others will require supporting facilities. One of the causes of the availability of facilities that do not yet support is the lack of budget support from the company. However, the relevant departments assume that the availability of facilities will be fulfilled by involving stakeholders in other departments in implementing the policy. It is known from the company's expectation that it will involve relevant departments in programs and services in labor. In addition, the involvement of labor and departments in organizing the program will also be one of the alternative strategy plans of the company in overcoming the availability of supporting facilities..

Conclusion

The research can be concluded that there are obstacles in the implementation of company policies when implementing policies on occupational safety and health and the work environment, including labor behavior, company support policies and the availability of company facilities. Labor is seen by companies as manpower who tend not to pay attention to regulations and do not care about the conditions of the work environment. This condition can hamper the company when implementing the company policy. Then, another obstacle in implementing the perceived policy is the absence of supporting policies. While policy improvements or improvements cannot yet be made in the near future, although it is felt by the company that the policy still has many shortcomings.

It can be known that the company or related department has defined several obstacles to policy implementation when implementing occupational safety and health policies and the work environment. These obstacles can be separated into two groups, they are internal obstacle and external obstacle. Internal obstacle is viewed from the absence of supporting policies from occupational safety and health regulations and the limited facilities in the work environment. While external obstacle is viewed from labor behavior that is still not sensitive to the issue of a safe work environment for work.

References

- Astuti, Y.H.N. 2010. Peran *safety* leadership dalam membangun budaya keselamatan yang kuat. Seminar Nasional VI SDM teknologi Nuklir Yogyakarta. ISSN 1978-1076.
- Badan Penyelenggara Jaminan Sosial (BPJS) Ketenagakerjaan Wilayah Kalimantan. 2017. Laporan Angka Kecelakaan Kerja 2014-2017. Balikpapan.
- Badan Pusat Statistik Provinsi Kalimantan Timur. 2016. Kalimantan Timur Dalam Angka.
- Barlasa B, Izcib FB. 2018. Individual and Workplace factors related to fatal occupational accidents among shipyard labors in Turkey. *Safety science* 101 (2018) 173-179.
- Blackmore, Ken. and Edwin Griggs. 2007. "Social Policy an Introduction". New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Bloor, M., & Wood, F. 2006. *Keywords in Qualitative Methods*. London: SAGE Publications Ltd.
- Chambers, Donald E. and Kenneth R. Wedel. 2005. "Social Policy and Social Programs : a Method for the Practical Public Policy Analyst". Boston : Pearson Education Inc.
- Creswell, J. W. 2009. *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Approaches (3rd Ed.)*. California: SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Di Nitto, Diana M. 2003. "Social Welfare Politics and Public Policy". USA: Allyn and Bacon.
- Extraktive Industries Transparency Initiative (EITI) Indonesia. 2016. Studi ruang lingkup laporan EITI Indonesia. Jakarta. Sekretariat EITI Indonesia Kantor kemeterian Koordinator Bidang Perekonomian RI.
- Fridayanti, N. dan Kusumasmoro, R. 2016. Penerapan Keselamatan dan Kesehatan Kerja di PT Ferron Par Pharmanceuticals. *Jurnal Administrasi Kantor*, 4(1): 211-234
- Friedrich, Carl J. 1963. *Man and Government: An Empirical Theory of politics*. New York: MacGraw Hill.
- dan Paul Terrel. 1993. "Dimensions of Social Welfare Policy". Massachusetts: Allyn
- Hadjimanolis, Boustra. 2013. Helath and safety policies and work attitudes in cypriot companies. *Safety science* 52 (2013) 50-56.
- Haslinda A. 2016. Safety Training, Company Policy and Communication for Effective Accident Management. *International journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Science* 2016 Vol 6, No. 9 ISSN 2222-6990.
- Iavicoli, Natalia, Deitingen, Maria R, Ertel, Jain, Lekat. 2011. Occupational helath and safety policy and psychosocial risk in Eurpe: The role of stakeholders perceptions. *Helath Policy* 101 (2011) 87-94.
- International Labour Organization. 2013. Modul Keselamatan dan kesehatan kerja "Keberlanjutan melalui perusahaan yang kompetitif dan bertanggungjawab. International Labour Office-Jakarta.
- International Labour Organization. 2018. Meningkatkan Keselamatan dan Kesehatan Pekerja muda. Jakarta.

- International Labour Organization .2003. Social Security and Coverage for All: Restructuring the Social Security Scheme in Indonesia Issues and Options, International Labor Organization, Jakarta.
- Jansson, B. 2008. "Becoming an Effective Policy Advocate: from Policy Practice to Social Justice". Pacific Grove, CA: Brooks/Cole.
- Jilcha K, Kitaw D. 2016. Industrial occupational safety and health innovation for sustainable development. *Technology an International Journal* xxx (2016) xxx-xxx.
- Johnson, Wayne .2008. *The Social Services: An introduction*, New York: FE Peacock.
- Kemeterian Energi dan Sumber Daya Mineral RI Direktorat Jenderal Mineral dan Batubara. 2018. *Data Statistik Kecelakaan Tambang 2018*. Jakarta.
- Kim, PH, Lee CS and Reynolds, PD. 2012. Backed by the state: Socchamberial Protection and Starting Businesses In Knowledgeintensive Industries. *Entrepreneurial Action Advances in Entrepreneurship, Firm Emergence and Growth*, Volume 14, 25–62.
- Kumar, Gupta, Agarwal, Singh, 2016. Categorization and standardization of accidental risk criticality levels of human error to develop risk and safety management policy. *Safety science* 85 (2016) 88-98.
- Midgley, James, Martin B. Tracy dan Michelle Livermore. 2000. *Introduction: Social Policy and Social Welfare*. London.
- Mokodompis GE. 2016. *Perlindungan Terhadap Tenaga Kerja Di Bidang pertambangan mineral dan Batubara menurut undang-undang Nomor 4 tahun 2009*. *Lex et Societatis*, Vol. IV/No. 5/Mei/2016.
- Nasr Hamid B. 2015. Labor protection and goverment control: Evidence from privatized firms. *Economic Modelling* xxx (2015) xxx-xxx.
- Patton, M. Q. 2002. *Qualitative Research & Evaluation Methods. Qualitative Inquiry (3rd Ed.)*. London: SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Prasud, Unggul & Subiharto, 2016. Peran Organisasi Dalam Menumbuh Kembangkan Budaya Keselamatan. *Buletin Pengelolaan Reaktor Nuklir*. Vol. 13 No. 1, April 2016: 1-11
- Silvestre. 2008. *Workplace and early Safety Policies in Spain, 1900-1932. Social history of Medicine* Vol 21 No. 1 pp 67-86
- Soepomo, 1999. *Pengantar Hukum Perburuan*. Cetakan ke 12. Penerbit Djambatan. Jakarta
- Tarwaka. 2012. *Dasar-Dasar Keselamatan Kerja serta Pencegahan Kecelakaan di Tempat Kerja*. Surakarta: Harapan Press
- Tawiah KA. 2016. *Occupational Health & safety and Oragnizational Commitment: Evidence from Ghanaian Mining Industry*.
- Taylor, S. J., Bogdan, R., & DeVault, M. L. 2016. *Introduction to Qualitative Research Methods: A Guidebook and Resource (4th Ed.)*. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Usep, Anggraini & Made, 2016. Model Perilaku Keselamatan Kerja Karyawan pada Industri Berisiko Tinggi. *Jurnal Manajemen Teknologi*, 15(1), 2016,51-66
- Widowati, 2010. *Perlindungan Jaminan Sosial Terhadap Tenagakerja Serta Penyimpangan Jam Kerja*. *Jurnal fakultas Hukum Universitas Tulungagaung* (57-81).
- Zastrow, Charles. 2010. "Social Work and Social Welfare". Canada: Brooks/Cole, Cengage Learning.

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